

Benchmark of the TDT MOC 3D solver of APOLLO3[®] against Serpent during depletion

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ABSTRACT

The Two-Three Dimensional Transport (TDT) solver of APOLLO3[®], based on the Method of Characteristics, has been recently extended to allow for full 3D neutron transport calculations during depletion using axial polynomial expansions for the neutron flux and macroscopic cross sections, thus reducing computational cost while preserving accuracy with respect to more traditional approaches. This work benchmarks the TDT MOC 3D solver against the Monte Carlo code Serpent on a classic PWR UOX assembly under depletion up to 60 GWd/tHM. After a detailed convergence analysis, optimal parameters are identified for both codes to balance precision and efficiency. Results show very good agreement: the effective multiplication factor remains within 140 pcm of the Monte Carlo reference, and discrepancies in radially integrated fission and capture rates are below 0.5%, dropping to less than 0.15% for the axially integrated rates. These findings confirm the robustness of the new TDT MOC 3D approach for depleted configurations and pave the way for extended benchmarks on more complex assemblies.

Keywords: APOLLO3[®], Serpent, MOC 3D, burnup, benchmark

1. INTRODUCTION

The long-term objective of achieving one-step core calculations with high-performance computing requires continuous improvements in deterministic neutron transport solvers. The recent advances in the TDT (Two-Three Dimensional Transport) solver of APOLLO3[®], the new generation multi-purpose deterministic code for reactor analysis developed at CEA with financial support from EDF and Framatome [1], mark significant progress towards this goal.

The Method of Characteristics (MOC) used in TDT was in fact extended to three dimensions [2], enabling 3D calculations in extruded geometries. An axial polynomial expansion for the neutron flux was later introduced, reducing computation time and memory consumption by limiting the number of axial meshes compared to step-constant axial representations [3]. This initial implementation was however limited to fresh fuel configurations: as burnup progresses, macroscopic cross sections develop strong axial gradients, especially at the interface with the axial reflector, that cannot be accurately represented with low-order methods, even when using refined meshes.

To overcome this limitation, the higher-order axial treatment has been recently extended to macroscopic cross sections [4], thus enabling the polynomial method to handle depleted systems while preserving its efficiency benefits. In continuity with [5], this work contributes to the benchmark of the TDT MOC 3D solver by assessing its precision on a realistic PWR assembly case under depletion conditions. The APOLLO3[®] results are compared with a Monte Carlo solution obtained with the Serpent code [6].

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The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we briefly recall the bases of the 3D polynomial MOC method implemented in TDT and describe the UOX assembly test case under investigation. Section 3 reports preliminary tests aimed at identifying the optimal set of computational parameters in both APOLLO3[®] and Serpent calculations. Depletion simulations being considerably time consuming, this accuracy-efficiency tradeoff is particularly important as small parameter adjustments can yield substantial time savings with minimal impact on results. Finally, we report and analyse the main results obtained on the depleted PWR assembly in Section 4.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND CASE STUDY

2.1. Principles of the axial polynomial MOC 3D method in TDT

The whole MOC 3D method implemented in TDT is based on the following space-angle moments expansion for the angular neutron flux ψ .

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) \approx \sum_{n=1}^{N_m} A_n(\boldsymbol{\Omega}) \Phi_n(\mathbf{r}), \quad \text{with } \Phi_n(\mathbf{r}) = \int \frac{d\boldsymbol{\Omega}}{4\pi} A_n(\boldsymbol{\Omega}) \psi(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}), \quad (1)$$

which is the classical flux expansion with respect to the set of real spherical harmonics $\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\Omega})$ truncated at order $N_m = (K + 1)^2$, with K being the maximum anisotropy order. Each angular moment is further expanded according to

$$\Phi_n(\mathbf{r}) \approx \sum_{p=0}^{N_p} P_p(\mathbf{r}) \Phi_{n,p,\mathcal{D}}, \quad \text{with } P_p(\mathbf{r}) = \left(\frac{z - \bar{z}_{\mathcal{D}}}{\Delta z_{\mathcal{D}}/2} \right)^p. \quad (2)$$

where N_p is the chosen maximum polynomial order, and the axial coordinate z is normalized in such a way that it ranges between -1 and 1 within each 3D computational region \mathcal{D} ($\Delta z_{\mathcal{D}}$ being the region's height and $\bar{z}_{\mathcal{D}}$ the midheight z value within \mathcal{D} , respectively). Macroscopic cross sections are expanded using the same polynomial basis as the flux, given the interdependence between the two physical quantities:

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{r}) \approx \sum_{p=0}^{N_p} \Sigma_{p,\mathcal{D}} P_p(\mathbf{r}). \quad (3)$$

This polynomial expansion is limited to the axial direction, as typical nuclear reactor geometries are extruded. On the radial plane, therefore, the classical step-constant approximation (i.e., a different constant value in each region) is still adopted for both flux and cross sections.

Trajectories are traced according to the strategy illustrated in Figure 1. For each 2D characteristic s on the x - y plane, the corresponding 3D characteristics are traced on the s - z plane, obtained by extruding s along the axial direction. After this, the classical power iteration scheme is used to solve the Boltzmann neutron transport equation, with the usual nested iterative structure consisting of outer, thermal, and inner loops. In TDT, convergence at each iteration level is accelerated by using a Double- P_N (DP_N) synthetic acceleration technique. We refer the interested reader to [4] for all details regarding the reformulation of the MOC transmission and balance equations, as well as the DP_N equations to incorporate the flux and cross-sections polynomial approximations.

Figure 1. TDT 3D tracking strategy (from [4]).

Figure 2. Radial layout (a,b) and vertical cut (c) of the 3D PWR UOX assembly test case.

2.2. Description of the assembly test case

In this work, a typical PWR assembly is analyzed, with UOX fuel enriched at 3.7% in mass, as shown in Figure 2. Radially, the problem consists of a 17×17 lattice (cell pitch of 1.26 cm and water blade of 0.04 cm) in all-rods-out configuration with an instrumentation channel at the center. Thus, only one-eighth of the lattice could be simulated, imposing reflection conditions at the boundaries and along the diagonal. In both codes, fuel rods were divided into four concentric rings in order to model burnup evolution with acceptable accuracy.

Axially, the assembly, whose active height is 3.92 m, presents six Zircaloy grids (with a height of 3.3 cm each, and radially modeled as circles around the fuel rods) and is surrounded by an axial reflector of 29 cm (consisting of two layers of different homogenized water-steel compositions). Only half of the assembly was simulated, applying reflective boundary conditions at the mid-plane ($z = 2.25$ m) and vacuum ones beyond the outer reflector ($z = 0$).

All materials were considered at a uniform temperature of 624 K, matching the available thermal scattering law data in the JEFF-3.1.1 nuclear data library [7] used for this study.

3. PRELIMINARY CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS

3.1. APOLLO3[®]

A development version of APOLLO3[®] based on v3.1 was used. We considered nuclear data condensed in 281 groups (according to the SHEM281 energy mesh [8]) taken from the CEAV514 library. A reduced decay dataset was used instead of the official chain, omitting ^{153}Gd , ^{165}Dy , and ^{131m}Te , not tracked by Serpent.

All calculations were run adopting a maximum anisotropy order $K = 3$ and a maximum polynomial order $N_p = 2$. Cross sections were nevertheless considered constant along z in the fuel grids to optimize the computational cost, as their axial gradient is supposed to be negligible throughout depletion in those regions.

For burnup calculations, we employed a predictor-corrector method similar to what described in [9],

adopting 4 substeps. A self-shielding calculation was repeated at each burnup step, adopting the Fine Structure model and the Livolant-Jeanpierre method for the resonant mixture treatment. Flux calculations were performed imposing a convergence criterion of 10^{-5} on the eigenvalue and the thermal and inner iterations precision, and of 10^{-4} on the fission integral precision.

The strategy to achieve convergent simulations with APOLLO3[®] was (i) start with the radial and axial material meshes used in [5]; (ii) study the impact on convergence of the flux solver parameters at zero burnup; (iii) refine the radial mesh using the identified parameters to ensure convergence at zero-burnup; (iv) perform a depletion calculation and compare results with the Monte Carlo reference.

The following MOC 3D tracking parameters and values were tested:

- Number of azimuthal angles (over π), N_φ : [18, 20, 24, 30, 36];
- Number of polar angles (over $\pi/2$), N_θ : [4, 5] (minimum 4 due to the P_3 anisotropy and the chosen Gauss-Legendre quadrature rule);
- Transversal trajectory step size in the x - y plane, Δ_{xy} : [0.01, 0.015, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.1, 0.2] cm;
- Transversal trajectory step size along z , Δ_z : [0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7] cm.

To assess convergence, both k_{eff} and radially integrated reaction rates (fission and capture) per axial layer were analyzed, but only k_{eff} results are reported here for the sake of conciseness. Table I summarizes the main results obtained. For each parameter, the run with the most accurate value is selected as the reference case. All other results are then compared with this reference by computing the relative difference $\left(\frac{k_{eff}}{k_{eff,ref.}} - 1\right)$ in pcm. Values in bold correspond to the options adopted in the study [5]. It can be observed that:

- k_{eff} remains stable when N_θ and Δ_z vary from [5];
- For $\Delta_{xy} = 0.07$, k_{eff} is far from convergence;
- For N_φ , relative differences are the largest, and even with 30 angles convergence seems far. Moreover, non-convergent behavior in integrated rates was found between 20–30 angles. These aspects required further analysis.

In MOC 3D, parameters are interdependent: for example, increasing N_φ requires finer Δ_{xy} . Thus, two cross-parameter studies were run (N_φ - Δ_{xy} , N_θ - Δ_z , see Table II). The latter pair showed convergence even with values from Table I. While, For $N_\varphi = 30$, convergence holds for $\Delta_{xy} \leq 0.03$ cm, but fails at 0.04 cm. The combination $N_\varphi = 30$, $\Delta_{xy} = 0.03$ cm is thus sufficient. Additional checks confirmed convergence for $N_\varphi = 30$, $\Delta_{xy} = 0.03$ cm (Table III), making it the default setup for APOLLO3[®] results in this work.

Finally, we tested several improvements on the radial mesh adopted for flux calculations with respect to [5]. The final adopted mesh, shown in Figure 2a, presents two major upgrades: (i) radial sectors arranged according to the widely used *windmill* mesh (to better model the flux thermalization at the cell corners); (ii) number of sectors in the guide tube cells increased to 8. The other tested options were the introduction of 2 annuli in the guide tubes and separately implementing 8 fuel rod sectors up to the fuel pin center. These investigations confirmed that the mesh reported in Figure 2a allows for convergence

Table I. TDT MOC 3D parameters convergence analysis.

N_φ	18	20	24	30	36	
k_{eff}	1.29573 (-41)	1.29570 (-43)	1.29603 (-18)	1.29605 (-16)	1.29626	
N_θ	4	5				
k_{eff}	1.29603 (-3)	1.29607				
Δ_{xy}	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.07
k_{eff}	1.29610	1.29611 (1)	1.29606 (-3)	1.29603 (-5)	1.29607 (-2)	1.29587 (-18)
Δ_z	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.7
k_{eff}	1.29602	1.29602 (0)	1.29603 (1)	1.29602 (0)	1.29603 (1)	1.29601 (-1)

Table II. TDT coupled parameters convergence analysis.

$N_{\phi}-\Delta_{xy}$	20-0.01	20-0.02	24-0.05
k_{eff}	1.29589 (-17)	1.29588 (-18)	1.29603 (-6)
	30-0.02	30-0.03	30-0.04
	1.29611	1.29612 (1)	1.29610 (-1)
$N_{\theta}-\Delta_z$	4-0.3	5-0.1	5-0.2
k_{eff}	1.29603 (-4)	1.29606 (-2)	1.29608

Table III. TDT parameter convergence analysis with $\Delta_{xy} = 0.03$.

N_{θ}	4	5	
k_{eff}	1.29606 (-5)	1.29612	
Δ_z	0.2	0.3	0.4
k_{eff}	1.29607	1.29606 (-3)	1.29607 (0)
$N_{\theta}-\Delta_z$	4-0.3	5-0.2	
k_{eff}	1.29606 (-6)	1.29611	

in k_{eff} and reaction rates.

3.2. Serpent

Serpent [6] is a continuous-energy Monte Carlo reactor physics code developed by VTT, Technical Research Centre of Finland. In this study, we adopted the Serpent-2.2.1 version (March 24, 2023). The code was executed in set `opti 4` (maximum performance), with unresolved probability table sampling. We used the Chebyshev Rational Approximation Method (CRAM) burnup mode, adopting the linear extrapolation, linear interpolation (LELI) predictor-corrector method with 3 predictor and 5 corrector substeps, as it provides an optimal accuracy-computational cost balance [9].

To make the default Serpent JEFF-3.1.1 library closely match the APOLLO3[®] CEAV514 one, the 52 additional nuclides sourced from other libraries were removed from Serpent's `.xsdata` file, except for ²⁵³Cf from ENDF/B-VII which is also present in the CEAV514 library. The Doppler-broadening was used to pre-process nuclides data at 600 K, the closest available temperature to the target 624 K.

In order to find a suitable reference to benchmark the MOC 3D solver of APOLLO3[®] under depletion, simulations were performed varying the number of axial layers. Increasing layers allows Serpent to model more distinct burnup zones and improves k_{eff} accuracy, since isotopic compositions evolve during burnup but are assumed constant within each region. However, finer meshes increase the number of zones, making simulations more computationally demanding. EDF's HPC cluster Cronos runtime being limited to 3 days per simulation, the neutron population had to be reduced as burnup zones increased. Thus, the reference configuration reflects a compromise between k_{eff} accuracy and computational feasibility.

The axial mesh configurations are given in Table IV, where set `pop` specifies neutron population per batch and number of batches, and $\sigma(k_{eff})$ is the k_{eff} uncertainty estimated as $N_{tot}^{-1/2}$. Inactive cycles were fixed at 300. The layering strategy used finer meshes near interfaces to capture flux gradients (see Figure 3). The "stepmesh" configuration is the one introduced in [5], where the APOLLO3[®] solution was compared to Tripoli-4[®] results.

Figure 4 shows k_{eff} evolution (solid lines) for the four axial meshes where the relative error curves (dashed lines) have their y -axis on the right. The 7065-zone, 45-fuel layer configuration was identified as the converged case. Convergence was defined as relative k_{eff} differences fluctuating around zero, with one configuration's values lying within the 3σ interval of another at each burnup step.

Table IV. Parameters of Serpent simulations for the axial mesh convergence analysis.

BU zones	Fuel layers	set pop ($\times 10^3$)	$\sigma(k_{eff})$ (pcm)
1099 (material mesh)	7	100 30	1.8
4082	26	200 9.5	2.3
7065	45	200 8	2.5
1208 (stepmesh)	77	200 6	2.9

Figure 3. Serpent: Fuel rod axial subdivision in 45 axial layers plus two reflector ones used for calculations.

Figure 4. Convergence of k_{eff} varying axial mesh (solid line: k_{eff} values; dashed lines: relative errors.)

Figure 5. Verification of the converged burnup mesh (solid line: k_{eff} values; dashed lines: relative errors.)

A time-dependent study was then performed to analyze burnup mesh effects. The mesh at convergence, resulting in 38 steps, was derived from [5], following the industrial rule limiting burnup step size to 2 GWd/tHM with the predictor–corrector method. To confirm convergence, it was compared against both finer (number of steps doubled) and coarser meshes. For the coarser mesh, refinement was retained up to 20 GWd/tHM to capture iodine, xenon, and gadolinium behavior at low burnup, but later steps were reduced (from four to three between each tens). Figure 5 compares the reference finer mesh (double steps), the 38-step mesh, and the coarse mesh with 10 predictor-corrector substeps). Results show that the 38-step mesh remains statistically consistent with the finest case, while the reduced-step mesh fails to converge. Based on these results, the following burnup mesh was identified as the convergent reference (38 steps, values in GWd/tHM):

0.0, 0.04, 0.12, 0.2, 0.5, 0.8, 1, 2, 4, 5.5, 7, 8.5, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, 20, 22, 24, 26, 28, 30, 32, 34, 36, 38, 40, 42, 44, 46, 48, 50, 52, 54, 56, 58, 60

4. BENCHMARK DEPLETION RESULTS

With the optimal simulation parameters selected as previously described, we performed comparisons between APOLLO3[®] and Serpent on the PWR assembly test case depleting up to 60 GWd/tHM. It turned out that a series of modifications were still necessary to improve agreement between the two codes, namely:

- in APOLLO3[®], subdivision of the reflector layers in two equally spaced layers to improve flux convergence and thus reduce the error on capture rate;
- in APOLLO3[®], addition of two burnup steps at 0.02 and 0.08 GWd/tHM to better model the xenon buildup and its high thermal neutron absorption. Serpent did not need these two extra burnup steps to ensure a convergent solution, as already framed in Figure 5;
- in both codes, change the energy deposition model to normalize at each burnup step only with fission energy (193.7201 MeV for ²³⁵U in APOLLO3[®] library), since the default normalization options are not coherent between the two codes.

The final results obtained in terms of k_{eff} are reported in Figure 6a. They were obtained by averaging Serpent results over 20 independent runs (each with 4000 batches and 200 000 neutrons each and 300 inactive cycles, yielding $\sigma(k_{eff}) = 3.5$ pcm) for a more reliable uncertainty estimate. The comparison

Figure 6. APOLLO3[®] vs. Serpent (the reference): (a) k_{eff} values and relative error during depletion; and (b) radially integrated rates values and error at 60 GWd/tHM.

Figure 7. Distribution of relative error on axially integrated reaction rates at 60 GWd/tHM ($3\sigma \approx 0.2\%$).

shows a generally low relative error, exceeding only 100 pcm between 20 and 40 GWd/tHM with a peak of about 140 pcm at 30 GWd/tHM. Figure 6b shows the relative discrepancy on the radially integrated, one-group fission and capture reaction rates. The rates are normalized so that the total fission rate is unitary for each set of results. Vertical light gray lines correspond to material layers (cf. Section 2.2), while gray bars centered at zero relative error represent the 3σ Monte Carlo statistical absolute uncertainty. The largest relative errors occur in the first two active layers near the reflectors (the second being a grid) for both fission and capture, while the remaining layers exhibit much smaller discrepancies.

Pin-wise reactions rates were also analyzed in each layer, but they are not shown here for conciseness. The maximum discrepancies reached 2.9% for fission and 4.8% for capture in the first grid layer, consistent with what shown in Figure 6b. Figure 7 reports instead the pin-wise distribution of the relative error on the axially integrated one-group reaction rates at 60 GWd/tHM: the maximum discrepancy is lower than 0.1% for the fission rate and around 0.15% for the capture one, while the mean discrepancy is ten times lower for the latter (for the former, it is almost null due to the renormalization). For both rates, the statistical uncertainty is $3\sigma \approx 0.2\%$.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

This paper has presented a first benchmark between the new TDT MOC 3D solver of APOLLO3[®] and Serpent on a classic PWR UOX assembly depleting up to 60 GWd/tHM, showing very promising results. The discrepancy on k_{eff} is very close to the Monte Carlo reference throughout depletion, with a peak of about 140 pcm at 30 GWd/tHM. The relative errors on one-group fission and capture rates are excellent as well, remaining within 0.5% in the most important axial layers, when considering the radially integrated rates, and even below 0.15% when considering the axially integrated ones.

The remaining k_{eff} deviations are most likely due to differences in evolution chains implemented in the two codes, as the isotopic concentrations extracted on a dedicated 2D fissile-cell test (not shown here) suggested. In terms of perspectives, further subdivision of the first two fissile layers near the reflectors in APOLLO3[®] could be explored to reduce the discrepancies shown in Figure 6b, while tests with depleting reflector treatment did not show significant improvement.

Future work will extend the benchmark to other assembly configurations (UOX-Gd, MOX) to assess APOLLO3[®]'s behavior. Preliminary tests performed on a UGD assembly suggest the need to adopt the Linear Surface MOC method [10] on the radial plane.

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